

SCRIPT CREACIÓN TABLAS DE IMAGEN RADIOLOGY EXTENSION

Tabla Radiology_Occurrence:

```
CREATE TABLE Radiology_Occurrence (
  radiology_occurrence_id          BIGINT          NOT NULL
CONSTRAINT RAD_OCCUR_PK PRIMARY KEY,
  radiology_occurrence_date        DATE             NOT NULL,
  radiology_occurrence_datetime    TIMESTAMP        NULL,
  person_id                         BIGINT            NOT
NULL,
  device_concept_id                 VARCHAR(25)     NOT NULL,
  radiology_modality_concept        VARCHAR(10)    NOT NULL,
  person_orientation_concept        VARCHAR(10)    NULL,
  radiology_protocol_concept_id     VARCHAR(64)    NOT NULL,
  image_total_count                 INT            NOT NULL,
  anatomic_site_concept_id          INT            NULL,
  radiology_comment                  VARCHAR(8000)  NULL,
  image_dosage_unit_concept          VARCHAR(4)     NULL,
  dosage_value_as_number             FLOAT          NULL,
  image_exposure_time_unit_concept  VARCHAR(5)    NULL,
  image_exposure_time                FLOAT          NULL,
  radiology_dirpath                  VARCHAR(255)   NOT NULL,
  visit_occurrence_id                BIGINT        NULL,
  device_manufacturer                VARCHAR        NULL,
  series_total_count                 INT            NULL
);
```

Tabla Radiology_Image:

```
CREATE TABLE Radiology_Image (
  radiology_image_id          BIGINT
  NOT NULL CONSTRAINT RAD_IMG_PK PRIMARY KEY,
  radiology_occurrence_id    BIGINT          NOT
NULL,
  person_id                  BIGINT          NOT
NULL,
  person_orientation_concept  VARCHAR(50)    NOT
NULL,
  image_type                 VARCHAR(500)    NULL,
  radiology_phase_concept    VARCHAR(32)    NULL,
  image_no                   INT            NOT
NULL,
  phase_total_no            INT              NULL,
  image_resolution_rows     INT              NULL,
  image_resolution_columns  INT              NULL,
  image_window_level_center VARCHAR(25) NULL,
  image_window_level_width  VARCHAR(25) NULL,
  image_slice_thickness     FLOAT           NULL,
  image_filepath            VARCHAR(255)    NOT NULL,
  radiology_series_id       INT             NULL,
  body_part_source_value    VARCHAR        NULL,
  laterality_concept_id    VARCHAR        NULL,
  series_type_concept_id   INT             NULL,
  series_type_source_value  VARCHAR        NULL,
  series_total_number      INT             NULL,
  series_serial_number     INT             NULL,
  condition_occurrence_id  BIGINT          NULL,
  observation_id           BIGINT          NULL
);
```

--A CONTINUACIÓN SE MUESTRAN LAS TABLAS Y SECUENCIAS AÑADIDAS POR
--VERATECH PARA LA CARGA DE LOS DATOS A OMOP.

```
CREATE TABLE correspondencia_pacientes (  
    source_id VARCHAR NOT NULL,  
    OMOP_id INT NOT NULL  
);
```

```
CREATE TABLE correspondencia_visitas (  
    source_id VARCHAR NOT NULL,  
    OMOP_id INT NOT NULL  
);
```

```
CREATE TABLE correspondencia_radiology_image (  
    source_id VARCHAR NOT NULL,  
    OMOP_id INT NOT NULL  
);
```

```
CREATE TABLE correspondencia_radiology_occurrence (  
    source_id VARCHAR NOT NULL,  
    OMOP_id INT NOT NULL  
);
```

-- SECUENCIAS:

```
CREATE SEQUENCE person_id  
START WITH 1  
INCREMENT BY 1  
MINVALUE 0  
MAXVALUE 999999999999;
```

```
CREATE SEQUENCE visist_occurrence_id  
START WITH 1  
INCREMENT BY 1  
MINVALUE 0  
MAXVALUE 999999999999;
```

```
CREATE SEQUENCE radiology_image_id  
START WITH 1  
INCREMENT BY 1  
MINVALUE 0  
MAXVALUE 999999999999;
```

```
CREATE SEQUENCE radiology_occurrence_id  
START WITH 1  
INCREMENT BY 1  
MINVALUE 0  
MAXVALUE 999999999999;
```

```
CREATE SEQUENCE condition_occurrence_id
START WITH 1
INCREMENT BY 1
MINVALUE 0
MAXVALUE 999999999999;
```

```
CREATE SEQUENCE measurement_id
START WITH 1
INCREMENT BY 1
MINVALUE 0
MAXVALUE 999999999999;
```

```
CREATE SEQUENCE observation_id
START WITH 1
INCREMENT BY 1
MINVALUE 0
MAXVALUE 999999999999;
```

```
CREATE SEQUENCE procedure_id
START WITH 1
INCREMENT BY 1
MINVALUE 0
MAXVALUE 999999999999;
```